

LAKBAY-DIWA ✦
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

JANUARY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488957
TIN 492-741-614
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[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18203662](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18203662)

The Evil Side of Deforestation

The natural beauty of nature that captivate and mesmerize the bold eyes of an individual in this world is something that we need to love, preserve and treasure. Allah swt gives us the opportunity to feel, experience, enjoy or even use His creations as far as human survival is concern. Indeed, the nature is one of the greatest creations and gifts of Allah swt for the entire humanity. People are able to survive in this world because of the overflowing blessings coming from the natural resources and people must put deep love and care for it. However, we cannot deny the fact that people are the number one destroyer and the cause of every devastations in our natural resources. In fact, one of those devastations that they usually observe and practice nowadays is deforestation. Obviously, our forests and mountains are getting sick and more problematic in which some people who unselfishly love and care natures feel enormous upset and condemn this kind of activities that continually existing in every communities around the world particularly here in the Philippines.

According to the United States Environmental Protection Agency, Deforestation defines as the clearing, destroying, or otherwise removal of trees through deliberate, natural, or accidental means. This implies that deforestation occurs a variety of reasons and has a variety of devastating consequences within the community. The rampant and vast cutting and removal of tress not just in mountains but also in lowlands lead to several destructions and natural calamities like soil erosion and coastal flooding that directly affect the healthy way of living of individuals within the community. In fact, trees help the land to retain water and topsoil in which provides the rich nutrients to sustain additional forest life. Without forest, soil erodes and wash away that may lead to several floods especially in the coastal areas.

Perhaps, according to several studies, the loss of habitat is one of the most dangerous and unsettling effects of deforestation. The loss of animal and plant species due to their loss of habitat may affect the 70% population of land animals and plant species live in the forest and probably, thousands of them will suffer or even died. In addition to this, the lack of trees allows a greater amount of greenhouse gases to be released into the atmosphere. Healthy forests absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, acting as valuable carbon sinks. Deforested areas lose that ability and release more carbon that leads to a more dangerous climate imbalance and change that can directly affect the whole world.

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Volume II, Issue I (January 2026), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

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It is pretty obvious that people love to live in a more comfortable and healthier environment but the question is, how can they achieve and have it if they continually destroying their environment particularly the forests that give life to the entire humanity. Simply, the negative actions of the people like deforestation manifesting negative consequences not just to the people but also to the other species living in the forest. Yet, it is not too late for us to put a solution to it.

Let us start educating people about the importance of forest and its contributions in our daily lives. People must understand the purpose of it and its significance to us. Aside from that is the effective and strict implementation of the existing laws that bans and prohibits the illegal cutting of trees should be observe and effectively implemented to all. The persons commit this kind of illegal activities must be punish according to the law.

Moreover, replanting trees must be observed and practice by the people in order to avoid or even stop deforestations. Through this we can simply help to preserve our forest and the species living in it or even save our lives in this world. Let us unite, cooperate and help one another in protecting our natural resources such as the forest to have better and healthier progress within our society without compromising our environment. Let us keep in our heart the value of everything that we can see in this world. The hope for better is within us and be part of those who aim for hope.